

JACQUES LACAN – LESSONS FOR COUNSELLING AND PSYCHOTHERAPY

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ABSTRACT

Jacques Lacan (1901-1981) is the most influential mind in the field of Psychoanalysis after Freud himself. His reinterpretations of ideas of the unconscious, the Oedipus complex, penis envy etc. give completion to Freud's inchoate concepts, and at times explain them better than Freud himself. His trailblazing exploits notwithstanding, his work has never been readily accepted in mainstream psychology. In spite of this Lacan's work is celebrated in fields as diverse as design, women's study and mass-media. The current paper presents a detailed introduction to Lacan's most important ideas viz. the mirror stage, the unconscious, and the Oedipus complex, as a foundation to discuss Lacanian Psychoanalysis and the lessons that can be drawn from it in modern-day practice. The author hopes that the paper serves as the starting point for a deeper, richer engagement with and critique of Lacan's contributions to psychotherapy.

Keywords: Lacan, Freud, Psychoanalysis, Counselling.

JACQUES LACAN – A DIFFICULT ANALYSAND TO DIAGNOSE

Jacques Lacan, as is widely recognized, is a theorist who is notoriously difficult to grasp. A part of this ‘difficulty to interpret Lacan’ emerges from the fact that most of what we know about Lacan’s theories comes from *Écrits* (1966) –a collection of second-hand accounts of Lacan’s fortnightly *Seminars* on Freud’s key concepts at Saint Anne Hospital between the years 1936 and 1966 by his son-in-law Jacques Alain-Miller. While *Écrits* is the best source of information on Lacan’s theories, and indeed the most widely known of his works in the English speaking world, Lacan did not take publishing his work very seriously, something that becomes evident from the fact that he referred to *Écrits* as a *poubellication*, a portmanteau of the French term for ‘dustbin’ *poubelle* and the word ‘publication’.

What makes *Écrits* even more perplexing for a novice is that it was originally written in French, which means that the English translations of his ideas are by no means a straightforward read, and one often gets the impression that Lacan meant to keep his ideas impossible to grasp in its entirety. Lacan in fact commented in a tongue-in-cheek manner once that ‘*Écrits* is not meant to be read’. In many ways, understanding Lacan’s ideas is as much of a challenge as psychoanalysis itself is to conduct. And in many ways, it is possible that that is what Lacan meant to achieve. His ideas always seem like a work-in-progress, and indeed Lacan never went on record to say that they were sacrosanct. For Lacan, no cow was too holy. While he called for a return to Freud, he himself reinterpreted some of Freud’s most basic concepts. But he applied the same yardstick to himself as well, and reinterpreted in entirety his own landmark concept of ‘the Mirror stage’ before the end of his career. In that sense, there are very few things that one can take as a given when it comes to Lacan. Interpretations of his ideas vary depending upon who the interpreter is, and one is expected to draw one’s own meaning from the basic building blocks of his theory.

ENGAGING ANEW WITH LACAN’S IDEAS

The current paper - the author’s attempt at understanding Lacan and drawing implications from his theory for counselling and psychotherapy, draws heavily from three chief sources – the first being Sean Homer’s guide to Lacan (2005): a simple, user-friendly introduction to those uninitiated to Lacan, the second Bruce Fink’s *Introduction to Lacanian Psychoanalysis* (1997): a logical progression once one is familiar with Lacan’s basic concepts and lastly Ian Parker’s *Lacanian Psychoanalysis: Revolutions in Subjectivity* (2011) which analyses the implications of Lacan’s work in modern day practice.

The paper begins with an explanation of the very need to study Lacan, and then goes on to offer as detailed a summary as possible of some of his key-concepts: the mirror-stage, the unconscious structured as a language, and his view of the Oedipal complex and its resolution. From there on, how the implications of these concepts shaped and influenced Lacan’s own psychoanalytic practice and

how they made his practice distinct from that of Freud shall be the focus. The paper ends with an account of the author's experience of engaging with the ideas of Lacan and the areas the author felt were not as clear as Lacan's other concepts rather than a critique because as Lacan himself put it, "When an analyst is unable to diagnose an analysand accurately, it is not because the analysand is on the 'borderline' it is because the analyst himself is not sure enough to commit here or there".

WHY STUDY LACAN?

While it is unarguably accepted today that Jacques Lacan is the single, most important name in the field of psychoanalysis after the legendary Sigmund Freud himself, Lacan's ideas were by no means embraced readily in the world of psychology. Such is the irony of Lacan's life that while he achieved acceptance in various fields of Humanities, unlike any other individual in the field of psychology, he was literally excommunicated from the field of psychoanalysis. Nonetheless, it cannot be denied that Lacan's work at once made psychoanalysis relevant to a whole new generation of theorists and therapists, at a point where alternate schools of therapy such as the cognitive-behavioral ones, or the humanistic ones sidelined Freudian psychoanalysis by terming it as abstruse, unstructured, unscientific and most recently not practical enough given the constraints of time and money the average individual seeking therapy faces.

Not one to treat any theoretical idea, his or another's, as untouchable, Lacan spent his career radically revolutionizing Freud's concepts; at times expanding them in directions Freud himself did not, while on other occasions offering an entirely fresh, contentious perspective on some of the most fundamental concepts of psychoanalytic theory and practice (Homer, 2005). While Lacan's sharp observations on psychoanalytic theory spared none, he at the same time brought Freud back into focus by challenging his critics to frame better critiques of Freud's theories than the done-to-death tirade that Freud focused excessively on sex and death (Parker, 2011). At the same time he challenged the so-called successors of Freud to engage directly with aspects of Freud's work that they had been previously handling with kid-gloves. He often accused post-Freudians of 'sanitizing' Freud's concepts in order to appear more appealing and scientifically sound to the behaviorists who stressed on making theory scientifically sound and therapeutic change 'time-bound and measurable'

Despite the best attempts of his contemporaries in psychoanalysis to sideline him and shroud his voice in sea of criticism, the fact that his work finds acceptance in fields as diverse as the study of film and literature, women's studies, studies on Marxism and politics and even the field of education makes even the most hardened of his critics to sit up and take notice of his ideas. Moreover, it encourages modern day students, therapists and researchers interested in the work of Freud to think beyond what is traditionally considered to be within the purview of psychoanalysis and engage with his works anew. (Homer, 2005)

With regard to the therapeutic aspects of Lacan's work, he is often criticized for his statement that the purpose of psychoanalysis is not to cure the client or adapt the client to the rational world. This is often misconstrued as Lacan washing his hands clean off any responsibility he may have towards the client as a therapist, but the truth of the matter is that he considered cure as a 'happy side effect of therapy but NOT the aim of analysis' (de Mijolla, 2005). He believed that if one, as an analyst conducts the analysis thoroughly well, symptoms will reduce and 'a cure' will be achieved. While other psychoanalysts too place the analyst on a pedestal calling him/her the expert, they also shift the burden of achieving the therapeutic change upon the client. For Lacan however, being the expert came with the responsibility of conducting the analysis thoroughly well. Everything else, he believed, would fall into place if the expert therapist was able to do that. That, if anything, puts the onus back on the therapist and NOT on the analysand.

Thus, while Lacan on one hand is certainly difficult to understand, his disinterest in defending his style has resulted in his ideas being misunderstood as the exact opposite of what he intended to put across. It therefore becomes important to engage with his ideas before deciding what can be incorporated into practice and what cannot.

THE MIRROR STAGE: LACAN'S VIEWS ON THE FORMATION OF THE EGO

The mirror stage is considered to be Lacan's first major innovation in the field of psychoanalysis. The first time he presented this idea was in the year 1936 at the Fourteenth Congress of the International Psycho-Analytical Association (IPA) whilst he was still a thirty-five year old psychoanalyst in training. The idea not only announced Lacan's arrival on the scene, it also contributed to him being perceived as an outcast for some, and a hero for some in the field of psychoanalysis. Conflicting accounts of what happened that day exist but what is widely known is that Lacan came up to present his paper title *Le Stade du Miroir* and was interrupted at the end of ten minutes by Ernest Jones, who was the president of the congress, Freud's biographer and one of his staunchest disciples (Homer, 2005: 17).

While it is not known whether he was interrupted simply because the time limit for each speaker was ten minutes or because Jones took offense to Lacan's radical interpretation of one of Freud's most fundamental concepts – the ego, Lacan nonetheless left the congress the next morning and did not submit his paper for the subsequent publication of the conference. All that was mentioned in the publication was that a certain Dr. J Lacan from Paris had presented a paper on *The Looking-Glass Phase* (Nobus, 1999). In a fitting sense, Lacan presented a revised version of the mirror stage thirteen years later in 1949 at the Sixteenth Congress of the IPA, once again presided over by Ernest Jones which today is considered the most widely cited of his works. The reason why it is important to know this backstory is that it shows that the mirror stage is an idea he honed and perfected over a period of thirteen years, before he decided to share it in its entirety with the world. Also in comparison to his output in the 1950s where Lacan was prolific both as a theorist and a therapist, the period of 1936-

1949 saw little output from Lacan, further showing that the Mirror stage is a masterpiece he spent a great deal of time and effort refining.

A one-line definition of what the Mirror stage does is that it explains the formation of the ego as a result of identification with an image of the self. Lacan's idea of the ego however contrasts with Freud's idea of the ego. According to Freud the ego was in many ways, a mediator between the primal, animalistic Id which demands that its desires be fulfilled whenever it wants and in exactly the way it wants regardless of the consequences, and the Superego which cites the moral demands of the external world to the Ego. The ego, according to Freud, worked as per the reality principle and the breakdown of the ego he felt, led to the development of psychopathology. Therefore Freud believed that coming into contact with the real world necessitates the formation of the ego, and if the ego breaks down, the individual becomes maladapted. For Freud, thus, the ego was helped the individual stay in touch with reality.

Lacan however turned the very concept of the ego on its head by stating that the ego is formed out of identification with an image of the self. Lacan believed that the formation of the ego occurs at the end of mirror stage which corresponds to the period of 6 to 18 months in a child's life (Homer, 2005) Lacan's idea of the Mirror stage was strongly influenced by the works of Henri Wallon during the 1940s who had tried to answer how self-awareness develops in a child. Wallon believed that the traditional idea that a child's sense of self-awareness arises out of his growing awareness of his own physical body presupposed that the child had a baseline level of awareness of its own body to begin with. Wallon argued that this meant that the child needed to not only have some awareness of his body and his bodily functions, but it also meant that the child had to have an awareness of his external environment and then somehow be able to distinguish himself from the environment, which could not be explained simply by saying that 'as bodily awareness increases, so does self-awareness' (Homer, 2005). Wallon was the first to put forth the idea that the child being able to recognize his own reflection in the mirror and then being able to distinguish that the image was external to him marked an important step in the formation of self-awareness of the child as the mirror image presents a dilemma to the child being both connected with the child's sense of self yet at the same time external. Wallon finally stated that from the ages of 3 months to one year a child moves from general indifference with his mirror-image to being captivated by it, to gaining a full mastery over the fact that the reflection in the mirror was separate from oneself. What Wallon could not however account for is why the mirror image is so fascinating to the child in the first place, especially around the half year mark. Also of note is the idea that other animals, such as primates do not recognize their own reflection in the mirror and often think of it as another creature. Another shortcoming in Wallon's idea felt by Lacan was that it did not explain how the concept of the 'self' emerges to begin with.

For that Lacan turned to the work of Alexandre Kojève who used to conduct seminars on the works of Hegel from 1933-1939. Hegel's most important contribution was the idea of *dialectics* which emphasized the unity of opposites. To simply put it, according to dialectics every idea (*thesis*)

produces its opposite (*antithesis*). In other words, when we speak of the 'self' we acknowledge the existence of a non-self, i.e. the other. Once we understand that the self is dependent on the existence of the other, a third idea that brings together 'self' and 'other' i.e. 'we' emerges (*synthesis*). This new idea once again becomes the opposite of another idea leading to a whole new chain of transformations. Kojève was in particular interested in Hegel's explanation of how self-consciousness emerged as a transition from animal existence to human existence. Kojève believed that for a human being to recognize itself as a human being, it must be recognized by another human being as one. Kojève compared this to the analogy of the Master and the Slave whereby the Master requires the Slave to recognize him as the Master to be considered a Master, whereas the Slave requires the Master to recognize him as his Slave to be considered as a Slave. The two therefore have a desire to be recognized by the other in order to be able to recognize themselves. Kojève considered this a fight unto death between desire and recognition. Lacan borrowed this idea of the eternal struggle between desire and recognition and stated that each human being is in the being of another (Homer, 2005). Kojève further went on to say that the reason why human beings attain self-consciousness and not animals is because in order to have one's desire fulfilled one must be able to express the desire as one's own. In other words, one must be able to say '*I want...*' to firstly be able to communicate to another being that a desire exists and that the owner of the desire is oneself (Nobus, 1999). Tying together the views of Wallon and Kojève thus, Lacan presented the idea of the Mirror stage.

Drawing from Wallon, Lacan said the child recognizing his own reflection in the mirror marked a critical moment in his development of self. But while Wallon suggested that this occurs from 3 months onwards to 1 year, Lacan chose to start the mirror stage at 6 months. The reason for him choosing 6 months as the critical moment was because in Lacan's theory 6 months marked the end of the first developmental phase and exposed the child to its first crisis, which Lacan called the 'weaning complex'. According to Lacan, when the mother withdraws the breast from the child, the child experiences a crisis because it at once is left wanting, yet is incapable of fulfilling these wants on his own. The resolution of this crisis believed Lacan occurred when the child develops a sense of *me* at the end of the mirror stage, after which it recognizes its desire for food as a personal conquest (Nobus, 1999).

The mirror reflection believed Lacan, offered the child a sense of solace after it is left feeling helpless as a result of the weaning crisis. This is because while the child in reality is incapable of controlling his whole body, the mirror reflection shows the child a 'whole' version of itself. Also being in control of the movements of the mirror image allows the child to feel a sense of mastery over its body that it has as yet not achieved. It is for this reason, believed Lacan, that the child is so fascinated by its mirror image at the age of six months or so. However, while the child is utterly fascinated by the mirror image, and identifies the reflection as his own, the reflection is an alienating own, in the sense that this is not the child's real self. None the less the alienated sense of self comes to be confused with the self and actually comes to take the place of the self. In other words, we acquire a sense of a unified

self at the cost of identifying with an-other. This according to Lacan is where the ego emerges. In sharp contrast to Freud's ideas, the ego is the product of an illusory sense of wholeness and mastery and its function is to maintain this illusion of mastery, lest the individual lose all control over the self (Homer, 2005). Also by relating the Mirror stage to the weaning complex, Lacan answered the critical question of why the child is willing to accept an illusory sense of itself in the first place. Thus as the subject emerges as a result of mis-recognition with an alienated sense of self, the subject is alienated in its very nature, or in other words, we exist as divided beings (Homer, 2005)

‘THE UNCONSCIOUS IS STRUCTURED LIKE A LANGUAGE’

After his innovation in the late 1949 – the mirror stage, Lacan put forth his next major idea in the 1950s when he emphasized the role of language in psychoanalysis and put forth the thesis that *the unconscious is structured like a language*. This idea of Lacan's was significantly influenced by the work of the anthropologist Claude Lévi-Strauss who in 1949 analyzed the marriage and kinship structures of so-called ‘primitive’ societies. Lévi-Strauss believed that what one observed through the marriage relations in these societies reflected the underlying structure of these societies. Lévi-Strauss pointed out that the exchange of women in these marriage rituals operated like a language, as if it were a formal system of rules and regulations which under no circumstances could be violated while at the same time the individual users who conformed to this set of rules and regulations remained unaware to this system. In other words, Lévi-Strauss argued that there is an underlying unconscious structure that determines people's relationships with one another, which the people themselves remain unconscious of (Homer, 2005). What Lacan learned from this was that there exists an unconscious structure that underlies all relations and all exchanges in these systems are not exchanges of real objects, but rather all exchanges are symbolic exchanges. This *symbolic function* believed Lacan intervenes all aspects of human life.

Lacan, who at that point, was trying to make psychoanalysis a scientific discipline, identified the unconscious as the subject of his study. He however, realized that in order for psychoanalysis to be considered a science, he had to specify how the object of study in this science could in fact be studied. For this Lacan turned to the work of Saussure in linguistics. Saussure, a revolutionary figure in the field of linguistics had suggested that language, as a system was complete at any given point in time, and its elements and rules were in theory at least, available to each individual user. In other words, said Saussure, whatever we say is said against a background of vocabulary, syntax, grammar and cultural variations in speech which determine what we can and cannot say and how we must say what we wish to say. However, when we speak we are not consciously aware of these rules. Saussure's most important contribution to the study of language was therefore the idea that language was a total system that governed what people said, while they themselves remained unconscious to its rules (Homer, 2005).

Language, according to Saussure, was a system of signs. These 'signs' consisted of two components, the *signifier* i.e. that which points to something, and the *signified* i.e. that which is being pointed at. Saussure mentioned that all words were signifiers in the sense that they pointed to something else. However they did not point to something that exists in the material world, rather they pointed to a concept. For example, the word 'tree' does not refer to a particular tree in the world, but the concept of a tree. The question that arises at this point however is that if words do not refer to actual objects in the real world, how are they consistently meaningful to a wide range of speakers? Saussure said that meaning does not reside in the signs themselves; rather each sign derives its meaning as a function of its difference from other signs. For example, a tree is different from a shrub, and a shrub from a bush. The meaning of each word also comes from the words that come before it and after it i.e. the way in which the words are ordered. For our words to convey a coherent message, we are bound by strict rules of communication. Thus three important aspects emerged from the work of Saussure. Firstly, language comes before conscious awareness i.e. we are born into language. Secondly, one produces one's experience within the constraints of a language system. And thirdly, language is not a system where a fixed, single meaning can be located; rather meaning changes in relation to the position of other signs (Homer, 2005).

Saussure's scientific approach to the study of language in this manner provided Lacan the means he required to define and study the unconscious. Lacan said that 'structure' in Saussure's ideas which governed what we say is nothing but the unconscious. The unconscious, he said was produced through language and governed by the rules of language. In other words, Lacan said that the world is arranged according to symbols that have emerged, and in effect everything is subject to the *symbolic order*. Everything in the world, including the unconscious, according to Lacan is ordered in accordance to the laws of the symbolic world. While Freud was of the idea that the unconscious is the part of our existence which escapes our understanding yet controls our behavior, Lacan believed that unconscious was made up of signifying materials, but its process of signification was beyond our control. In other words, the unconscious is the discourse of the Other which speaks through the Subject. The subject however can never fully assimilate the discourse of the other. We are therefore born into language – a system used by others to articulate their desires, and must learn to articulate our own desires using this system as well. Though as subjects, we cannot escape this system, the system escapes us no matter how well we grasp it (Homer, 2005).

Taking forth the idea from the mirror stage that the ego is not central, Lacan suggested that the term *I* – a referent of self-awareness or ego, did not really refer to anything in language at all. In other words he distinguished between the subject who speaks (signifier), and a subject who is spoken of (signified). Consistent with his earlier idea that the signifier takes precedence over the signified, Lacan decentralized the *I* or the ego stating that the subject can never speak of the structure of the language rather the structure of the language speaks of the subject. In other words, the ego can never speak of the unconscious; rather it is the unconscious that speaks through the subject (Homer, 2005).

As we will see later, the idea from the mirror stage of ‘an essentially divided self’ along with the notion that ‘unconscious is the object of study in psychoanalysis’ significantly shapes Lacanian psychoanalytic practice. Before discussing Lacanian Psychoanalytic practice however, we must discuss one last significant aspect of Lacanian theory i.e. the Oedipal complex.

OEDIPUS COMPLEX AND THE MEANING OF THE PHALLUS

Freud’s concept of the Oedipus complex is simultaneously the most popular as well as the most controversial aspects of his work. For many theorists, the idea that the child sexually desires the mother was an instant deal-breaker which contributed significantly to the sidelining of Freud. Even more controversial was the concept of ‘penis envy’ which has been lambasted over the years by feminists for allegedly promoting the supremacy of the phallus. The controversy surrounding the concept of ‘penis envy’ even prompted post-Freudians such as Karen Horney to suggest a counter- concept of ‘womb envy’. Amidst it all, Lacan’s views on the Oedipus complex which not only explain Freud’s own concept in a much better light, but also in fact suggest a more socially equal explanation of the oedipal phenomenon, have been lost somewhere amongst all of these arguments.

Lacan began his own explanation of the Oedipus complex by reinterpreting the term ‘phallus’ in itself. For Lacan, the phallus was not equal to the male sexual organ, though it was related to it in a way. Similarly, whereas in Freud’s conceptualization of the Oedipal complex, the father referred to the actual father, Lacan used the father as a metaphor. The term he used specifically was *nom de père* which in French means ‘Name of the Father’. What is also interesting to note is that Lacan plays on the similar sounds of the terms *nom* meaning ‘name’ and *non* meaning ‘no’ in French. Indeed the idea of *nom de père* is closely linked with the idea of *le non du père* which refers to the restrictive and prohibitive nature of the Name of the Father as will become evident shortly.

Lacan describes how at first there exists a simple dyadic relationship between the (m)other and the child. The child, says Lacan, assumes that it is one with the (m)other and assumes that since the mother fulfills all its desires, it must be the sole object of the mother’s desire. However, when the child sees that the desire of the mother is directed elsewhere viz. towards the father, this simple dyadic relationship between the mother and the child is turned into a triangular relationship by the Name of the Father. The child assumes that since the mother’s desire is directed towards the father, the father must possess something that the mother lacks. This object of the mother’s desire is what Lacan refers to as the *imaginary phallus*. The reason why this is called the imaginary phallus is because it firstly goes beyond the meaning of the male sex organ and secondly it is an imagined object that exists nowhere in reality. The child therefore attempts to go back to the dyadic relationship it shared with the mother by trying to become the object of the mother’s desire once again i.e. by becoming the imaginary phallus. At this point the child believes that the imaginary phallus is something that has been lost and can be gained once again.

This is where Lacan introduces his idea of castration anxiety. For Lacan castration is not the fear of having one's penis physically severed by the Father but rather the renunciation of the idea that the imaginary phallus can be attained. In other words, castration anxiety is the anxiety the male child faces when it realizes that he lacks and can therefore never become the object of the mother's desire once again. The phallus therefore is a signifier of lack according to Lacan (Homer, 2005). The concept of the Name of the Father is a particularly important one in Lacan's work as it is the intervention of this concept that breaks the child's illusory notion of unity with the (m)other and brings him into the symbolic realm as a subject that lacks. The Oedipus Complex for Lacan thus is the replacement of one signifier – the desire of the (m)other with the installation of the Name of the Father. Lacan considered the Name of the Father as the central organizing factor of the unconscious, and its presence or absence is tied to the development of psychopathology.

What comes next however is how Lacan tackled the prickly issue of how the concept of penis-envy which promoted phallic supremacy. Lacan did this rather tactfully by starting off in agreement with Freud's concept, but then diverging from it at key points. While Lacan agreed with Freud's notion that there was no signifier of feminine sexuality, his views on castration anxiety ensure that female sex is not considered secondary to the male sex in any way. Lacan in fact said that the only signifier of sex is masculine, and the signifier of masculinity is a signifier of lack. In other words, according to Lacan, it is men who are castrated or lack, and not women. Lacan clearly suggests that castration occurs on the male side and that females enjoy a much greater freedom from this concept than do males. The next question that emerges is how then does a girl child experience a sense of lack? Lacan explains that the interaction with the Name of the Other leaves both sexes with a feeling of lack. For the male child, they receive the symbolic phallus from the father which is a signifier of masculinity but also a signifier of lack. Whereas in the case of girls, they receive no such signifier from the Name of the father, which is also seen as lack. Both these feelings of lack are equivalent to 'castration anxiety'. Therefore, for Lacan castration is not a binary sense of having or not having the phallus, rather it is a dialectic concept such that the males possess a phallus that signifies lack, whereas the females have the phallus in not having it, in other words, they possess lack (Moncayo, 2008).

The resolution of the Oedipal complex for men occurs when a shift occurs from seeing the mother as a lacking other to seeing the father as the possessor of the imaginary phallus. By recognizing with a sense of lack, boys 'pretend' to have phallus so that they can become the object of desire for other women. For girls on the other hand the resolution is a result of the acceptance that they are not the imaginary phallus, nor that they can have the imaginary phallus possessed by the Father. They must therefore become the phallus for the other. In other words, they must become the object of desire for other men (Homer, 2005).

The corollary of this is that we either try to make the other the object of our desire, or try to become the object of desire for the other. However, there is always a significant gap between what men and women desire from each other. And therefore, there is no such thing as a fulfilling sexual relationship

according to Lacan. This is because the Name of the Father which installs the Superego is in itself what encourages us to desire. Borrowing from dialectical thought once again Lacan suggests that the desire to break the law is the very precondition for the existence of the law in itself. Therefore while the Superego forces us to suppress the desire of the Id, or to give up the idea of the imaginary phallus, it at the same time compels us to chase our *jouissance*. As a result, we always chase *jouissance* and can never achieve it fully within the rules and regulations of the world (Homer, 2005)

KEY CONCEPTS IN LACANIAN PSYCHOANALYSIS

a) Desire of the analyst as a driving force in therapy

One of the first things that makes Lacanian Psychoanalysis at once distinct and even incomprehensible for someone anchored in a non-Lacanian school of thought is the notion of the ‘desire of the analyst’. While most schools of therapy consider the client’s intrinsic desire to change as the starting point and the driving force of therapy, Lacan’s view is the exact opposite. The popular belief is that no amount of therapy or psychoanalysis can do any good to the client as long as he/she remains resistant and does not desire to change. This in particular is the reason why personality disorders and addictions are considered exceedingly difficult to treat by modern day therapists.

Lacan’s view on the other hand is ‘Of course the analysand does not desire to change!’ (Fink, 1997: 3). Lacan believes that if an analysand is displaying symptomatic behaviors it means that a great deal of energy has been invested into those symptoms. The analysand cannot simply be convinced to give up the satisfaction he/she derives from experiencing the symptoms. In other words, while an analysand may approach the analyst stating that he/she wants to be relieved of certain symptoms, what he/she really means is that they want the therapist to ensure that they do not give in to the desire to indulge in symptomatic behaviour once again. The dominant tendency of the analysand is to therefore not rock the boat. Of course this is not to state that the analysand is always aware of the fact that he/she experiences some level of enjoyment from the symptoms, nor does it mean that the it becomes readily evident to the analyst. What this means therefore is that the therapist cannot rely on some sort of intrinsic desire to change or a will to get better on the part of the analysand to drive therapy forward.

Lacan believes that often the time when an analysand approaches an analyst is when they have no will to live, no desire to move forward, and do not see a way to move forward even if they wished to. He therefore makes it clear that the ‘desire of the client to change’ can never serve as the driving force of therapy. If anything, believes Lacan, it is the analyst’s desire that drives therapy ahead. (Fink, 1997)

Here once again, there is a tremendous scope to misunderstand what Lacan is saying. The source of this confusion is often a result of misidentifying the concept of ‘desire of the analyst’ with the analyst communicating to the analysand what he wants them to do, thereby putting forth his own agenda. While it is certainly the analysand’s agenda that must be the focus of therapy, and it is widely

accepted that the analysand is free to leave therapy anytime he wishes, it is often essential to therapy that the analysand loses a desire to leave therapy altogether. To look at this in an optimistic manner, this may at times be because the analysand no longer feels the need to remain in therapy, and to view it negatively it may well be that the analyst did something unwise to make the analysand wish to leave therapy, but more often than not, said Lacan, the analysand is looking for an excuse to leave therapy. It is therefore the analyst's desire and not their own diminishing sense of enthusiasm that drives them to continue with therapy. An example of how the desire of the analyst serves to maintain the analysand in therapy as shown by Fink, is how the analyst saying 'I'll see you tomorrow' brings back the analysand the next day to therapy even though he may not feel there is anything left to speak to the therapist (Fink, 1997: 4)

Lacan however advises caution with regards to the use of the desire of the analyst to drive therapy forward with specific clients. With neurotic patients, says Lacan, the analyst must always express a desire to see the analysand again, even if he feels that the analysis has achieved all that it could at that point. Lacan believed that the moment the analysand felt that he no longer requires to be in therapy and the desire becomes overpowering, he himself will discontinue therapy and if this does not happen it either means that the analytical work is not done yet, or that the analysand has developed a strong dependency on the analyst. In any case, Lacan suggests that the analyst has to be tactful in expressing his desire to the client. He likened the analyst to an actor who may or may not convey his true feelings to the client. In other words, even though an analyst feels negatively towards the analysand, communicating this to him is of no use. The analyst must therefore maintain a perpetual state of desire – a desire for the client to talk, dream, fantasize, freely associate and interpret; regardless of his own feelings towards the client for this is the driving force of therapy (Fink, 1997:5)

b) The Analytical Relationship

In Lacanian Psychoanalysis, though the therapist is considered an expert and it is the desire of the therapist that is considered the motor force that drives therapy, it does not rely on the analysand's belief in the expertise and healing power of the analyst. Rather Lacan suggests that *the subject (who is) supposed to know something of importance in psychoanalysis is the analysand's unconscious* (Fink, 1997:30). In other words, the only authority to be respected in the psychoanalytic setting is the manifestation of the analysand's unconscious through slips of tongues, mistakes, omissions etc. The final authority in a psychoanalytic session is therefore the analysand's unconscious and not the ability of the analyst to immediately grasp what the analysand is saying, interpret it and identify the symptoms it points to.

The role of the analyst in the initial stages of therapy in fact is to decenter the subject and emphasize the unconscious. The earliest interventions of the analyst involve the use of what Lacan describes as *punctuation*. This is the speaking equivalent of quickly underlining a particular word, omission, neologism or peculiarity in the speech of the analysand in order to draw more attention to that aspect.

It may be in the form of an interested ‘Huh?’, or as the repetition of a few words or repetitive homonymic sounds, or even numbers. The analyst as a result is required to be tuned in at all times to what the analysand is saying and also be acutely aware of material in the unconscious is organized. Moreover, by emphasizing slips of tongue, slurs, double entendres etc. the analyst conveys the idea that he has not interpreted the meaning of what the client has said, thereby encouraging him to pay attention to unconscious utterances and meanings that he has been as yet inattentive to (Fink, 1997:15).

Yet another early intervention the analyst uses to bring the unconscious into focus is *scansion*. In simple terms scansion refers to the analyst interrupting free association whenever he believes that what is being shared is of significance and requires greater thought and attention by the client. While this may at first seem paradoxical to the idea of free association, one needs to tie it with the concept of the analyst’s desire as the driving force in therapy. In the early stages of therapy, states Lacan, the analysand can be prone to filling up their sessions with empty chatter. By interrupting at points where the analyst feels that something of importance is being spoken of, the analyst expresses the aforementioned desire to hear about that topic. Here it must be noted that the analyst does not really have a personal interest in hearing a particular topic rather, the desire of the analyst is to bring the unconscious to the fore. The role of the analyst is to emphasize the manifestations of the unconscious. This may at times lead to the analysand viewing the analyst as the agent of the manifestation of the unconscious. The analysand refuses to take the responsibility for dreams, slips of tongue, slurs etc. blaming (or projecting responsibility onto) the presence of the analyst for their manifestation. The role of the analyst is to therefore make the unconscious present through his presence. Insofar that the analyst comes to stand in for the unconscious, the ‘person’ of the analyst must disappear and the analyst must become an abstract Other who speaks whenever there is a slip or a crack in the analysand’s discourse (Fink, 1997:30).

The analyst must therefore keep their personal feelings, likes/dislikes, and personality traits out of the way as each individualizing feature of the analyst thwarts the analysand’s projection of the unconscious. The more the analysand perceives the analyst as being similar, the less likely that the analyst will be seen as the Other. The analyst must therefore be careful not to interact with the analysand in a way any of the ‘others’ in his life have done. This means that the analyst must be vigilant for signs of transference. At the same time, analysands try to get the analysts to judge them. However such judgments or countertransferences too are to be avoided if the analyst is to come to stand for the Other (Fink, 1997)

c) A brief overview of the Lacanian approach to diagnosis

The Lacanian approach to diagnosis is certainly not comparable to diagnostic systems such as the DSM and the ICD where every clinically visible symptom or set of symptoms is said to stand for a

separate disorder. Rather it is a minimalist diagnostic schema. Lacan's diagnostic schema consists only of three broad categories, *Neurosis*, *Psychosis* and *Perversion* (Fink, 1997: 75).

Yet another distinct difference between the Lacanian diagnostic schema and others is that there exists no continuum between neurosis and psychosis. All three categories are considered distinct from one another, and the approach the analyst must take in every case is distinctly different from the other. What makes diagnosis even more important is that the techniques that are believed to work with neurotic clients are not believed to work with psychotic clients. Therefore situating the analysand as either neurotic, psychotic or perverse is crucial in helping the analyst determine the course of action that must be taken with each client. These three categories of neurosis, psychosis and perversion are based primarily on Freud's work and the mechanisms that are believed to lead to the development of each of them too have been suggested by Freud himself.

Neurosis is said to be a result of repression. What is repressed however is neither perception nor affect; rather thoughts about the perceptions of the real world are repressed. And since these thoughts cannot be expressed in the form of words, the repressed returns and expresses itself in the form of symptoms. Though this by no means is an exhaustive account, the general explanation offered is that if the symptoms are expressed in the body, conversion symptoms emerge; if they express through the mind obsessiveness emerges; and when they express through the body and mind hysteria emerges (Fink, 1997: 112-140).

Psychosis on the other hand is a consequence of what Lacan describes as *foreclosure*. Foreclosure according to Lacan is the radical rejection of a particular element from the symbolic order which in a way anchors the symbolic order as a whole i.e. the Name of the Father. When an individual is no longer anchored in the realm of the symbolic, Lacan believes the tell-tale symptoms of psychosis i.e. hallucinations and language disturbances start to emerge. (Fink, 1997:79)

Finally perversion is said to be a consequence of *disavowal*. Disavowal, also a form of negation as is the case with repression and foreclosure, is often interchangeably used with the term denial. Indeed disavowal is rejecting the reality of a perception on account of its potentially traumatic associations. Freud exemplified disavowal best in the case of Little Hans where Hans rejected the perceptual evidence that his seven-month old sister did not possess a penis. The pervert disavows perceived objective reality and refuses to give up *jouissance*. For example, a young boy who gets caught by his mother touching himself and is threatened that the Father will cut his penis off, would in a normal scenario give up the pursuit of phallic *jouissance* at the intervention of the Name of the Father. The pervert however disavows the Name of the Father, as if it has not been registered at all. Perversion, like psychosis was believed to emerge out of the inadequacy of the Name of the Father to get the child to give up the pursuit of the (m)other. The pervert therefore continues pursuing the (m)other either through incestuous desires or through fetishes that substitute the (m)other (Fink, 1997:174)

The Lacanian diagnostic schema is often criticized for not having clear distinctions between the three categories that allow diagnoses to be made with any degree of certainty. Lacan's counter to this was that it is for the analyst to become familiar with them and thereby be able to discern them with one another.

d) The Variable Length Session

This free-hand licence given to Lacanian psychoanalysts to interrupt free association in order to separate the wheat from the chaff in a therapeutic session, is what led to the formulation of one of Lacan's most controversial therapeutic innovations *the variable length session*. The practice of variable length sessions was a reaction to the Freudian '50 minute hour' which like many of Freud's concepts had become too holy a cow to touch. The concept of variable length sessions is based on the belief that the only expert in the psychoanalytic setting is the unconscious of the analysand, and that the focus of the analyst is to ensure that the focus of therapy sessions is the discourse of the Other. In that sense, the variable length session may be viewed as an extreme version of *scansion* whereby the therapist abruptly interrupts the session to emphasize the fact that the focus must be on the discourse of the Unconscious.

The other way of looking at it is that the unexpected ending of a session leaves the analysand with an absence, a cut in free association, and a question of why the analyst ended the session there. The analysand naturally then will focus on the gap and try to understand what had to be expressed but could not get expressed. In a way this indirectly communicates the desire of the analyst to discuss a particular issue in greater detail, without the analyst having to directly say so to the client. The variable length session is an important tool in Lacanian Psychoanalysis as it works without a predefined set of objectives. Quite simply put, a Lacanian psychoanalytic session is focussed around absences and gaps in the narrative of the analysand. Lacanian psychoanalysts therefore do whatever it takes to not allow the client to slip into a comfort zone where they do not have to mull over the meaning of a slip of tongue, a slur, an omission etc. (Parker, 2011).

A final idea that must be kept in mind when it comes to the variable length session is that unlike what Lacan's critics have said about it, it is not necessarily a 'short session'. The term variable in fact implies that session can even span a few hours.

CONCLUDING THOUGHTS

Engaging with the ideas of Jacques Lacan is simultaneously challenging as well as utterly fascinating. The journey is likely to be dotted with moments of bewilderment and 'A-ha' moments in equal measure. Like a typical Lacanian psychoanalysis session would do for an analysand, Lacan's ideas require one to come out of one's comfort zone.

Lacan's ideas such as the 'desire of the analyst as the driving force in therapy' at once disallow the therapist to blame the client's 'lack of motivation' for the failure of therapy as well caution one not to fall prey to countertransference and the God complex. Similarly while the assertion that 'Lacanian psychoanalysis does not aim to cure or adapt the client' may sound like a disavowal of responsibility for producing any fruitful therapeutic change, assertions such as 'cure is a happy side-effect of a well conducted analysis' place the onus back onto the analyst.

Most significantly Lacan's ideas on therapy often provoke much deeper thoughts on a wide range of issues concerning human existence. His tactfulness in dealing with some of Freud's most controversial ideas such as penis envy and turning them into an empowering concept rather than weakening one is an unparalleled stroke of genius in the field of psychoanalysis. The only unfortunate aspect is that the work of Lacan is celebrated in every field apart from psychology be it media studies, women's studies or even design. The author is of the hope that this paper serves as a starting point for a richer discussion and critique of Lacan's work by other researchers and students alike.

REFERENCES

- de Mijolla, A. (2005). Cure. In A. de Mijolla, *International Dictionary of Psychoanalysis*. Gale Cengage.
- Fink, B. (1997). *A Clinical Introduction to Lacanian Psychoanalysis*. Cambridge/London: Harvard University Press.
- Homer, S. (2005). *Jacques Lacan*. New York: Routledge.
- Moncayo, R. (2008). *Evolving Lacanian Perspectives for Clinical Psychoanalysis: On Narcissism, Sexuation, and the Phases Faces of Analysis in Contemporary Culture*. London: Karnac Books.
- Nobus, D. (1999). *Key Concepts of Lacanian Psychoanalysis*. New York: Other Press.
- Parker, I. (2011). *Lacanian Psychoanalysis: Revolutions in Subjectivity*. East Sussex: Routledge.